

MANDALA TV: INTERACTIVE LOCAL TELEVISION IN CIKAJANG, GARUT

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Abstract

Mandala Vision is local television services operating in Cikajang, Garut Regency. They has its own channel that created and managed independently called Mandala TV. This channel does not present usual contents like another television in Indonesia. Its contents are local event documentation, Islamic preaching, wayang puppet show and music videos such as dangdut, Sundanese pop songs and Indonesian songs. Based on this circumstance, we decided to analyze those contents by Robert K. Yin's Case Study design. Research showed, first, Mandala TV's contents were freely selected by its operator based on what they want and audiences request. Second, they get contents from internet, except local event documentation is self-produced. Third, there are no gatekeeper and guideline for deploying contents. In the brief, contents from Mandala TV creates an interactive atmosphere in local television. Then, local event documentation makes Mandala TV become an effective channel for spreading information to audiences in Cikajang, because its proximity. Local television industry like Mandala TV is an opportunity to share value and unite people in a region.

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1. Introduction

Mandala TV is one of channels from Mandala Vision cable television services. Its operated by Mandala Haji Vision company. Mandala Vision's head office located in Bandung, it has branches in several regions such as Sumedang, Ciwidey, Leles, and Cikajang. In other regions of Indonesia there also cable television company named Mandala Vision owned by different people who are fellow business partners.

Mandala Vision provide dozens channel, either Indonesian television channels or foreign television channel. There were one channel that broadcasting local content named Mandala TV. This channel mostly broadcasting music video and islamic preaching, but. local contents can still be found. This channel were available in every Mandala Vision branches. Audiences were able to sent request and greetings to be aired on Mandala TV. This makes many people using Mandala Vision's services, also because of the cheap cost compared to other cable television services or satellite television services. The audience were charged 40.000 rupiah monthly to use Mandala Vision services.

This research focus on Mandala TV Cikajang because there are many local contents aired in Cikajang and because of proximity with researchers. Mandala TV Cikajang has been

operating for four years. Many local contents, audience requests and greetings aired. Audience feedback can be seen from requests and greetings sent to Mandala Vision.

2. Methods

This research use qualitative method with case study approach. Yin case study approach[7] used to analyze how Mandala TV produced content and how it worked. Object of this research is Mandala TV's contents. Research started with contents observation for 2 weeks in random time, then, interview with Mandala Vision Cikajang's employees. The data from observation, interview and other literature then triangulated to see how Mandala TV's contents worked. This research does not represent Mandala TV's broadcasts in other branches because there may be circumstances difference.

3. Results

Mandala TV is one of 41 channels available in Mandala Vision services. 40 channels obtained from 4 satellites, meanwhile mandala TV's channel directly processed by administrator computer. It makes Mandala TV 's channel itself has different quality of picture, it tend to be more opaque than another channels.

Mandala TV independently operated by Mandala Vision's employee. There is no operation procedure for broadcast or rules, therefore it makes Mandala TV free for operation. Mandala TV has no broadcast schedule, but administrator always airing religion's contents on Friday and wayang puppet show on Saturday night.

Mandala Vision Cikajang itself has 10 employees consist of 6 technicians, 3 collectors and one administrator. The Administrator who managed the broadcast. In the practice, the administrator is free to broadcast any contents based on what they want or what the on-duty employees of Mandala Vision want.

Broadcasted contents usually like dangdut music video, Sundanese pop music video, Indonesian music video, foreign music video, Islamic preaching, wayang puppet show and local event documentation. The contents gained by downloading on the internet except the local event documentation that usually self-produced by the Mandala Vision's employees. Furthermore, there is "Salam-Salam", it means message or greetings from audiences in the form of running text showed in the middle of the broadcast.

Local event documentation that has aired on Mandala TV is inter-village football game at Cikajang, volleyball game and the celebration of Indonesia independence day at Cikajang. The events are recorded by Mandala TV's employee using handycam. The record later aired after reviewed by the administrator. There are no content guidelines, so that the regulator itself depends on Mandala Vision employees.

They are stored the content they have been gathered at the administrator's computer, categorized by broadcast type. Then, they insert the content that to be aired to DeeJay System application playlist. The absence of broadcasting procedure makes the content can be changed at any time.

Mandala Vision receives content request or greetings from the audience through administrator or office phone number. If the content they request are available on the administrator's computer, the content will be broadcast instantly. Meanwhile, if the content they request unavailable, it will be aired after the administrator downloaded the content. About 2.500 customers Mandala Vision around Cikajang could send requests or greetings.

Mandala Vision also accepts the content produced by the audience to aired on Mandala TV. The audience-produce content that has been aired such as the celebration of independence day of Indonesia at Kampung Panday, Cikajang. The documentation broadcasted without any editing process. The audience could request their activities got recorded and aired on Mandala TV by sending a proposal to the Mandala Vision main office.

There is no specific budget for managing Mandala TV, because they got free content from the internet. There is no specific equipment for Mandala TV broadcast, so there is no specific budget needed. Mandala Vision opens the advertisement space at Mandala TV, but since it's established, there were only one ad that have been aired at Mandala TV Cikajang. The advertisement received by main office, then distributed to the Mandala Vision branch. Mandala TV airing the ads at the time determined by the main office.

4. Discussion

Flexibility in the Mandala TV totally different with another television. Broadcast media like television and radio are media that have a strict duration calculation[2], both of the content or ads calculation. Meanwhile Mandala TV is not attached to the schedule. The contents could be aired and switched whenever they want or based on audience request. There is a islamic preaching on Friday and wayang puppet show on Saturday night which is not a specific schedule because it could be changed at any time.

When researchers did the observation on August 2018, the administrator shows us the 2016 inter-village football game's documentary at Cikajang. The event recorded by the Mandala TV employee and then aired. The documentation itself replaces dangdut music video that aired before.

There are no rules or guidelines about eligible content on Mandala TV, it's all depends the administrator and employee's desire and agreement. Based on the observation, if the content doesn't contain a problem could be aired, including requested contents by the audience. The Administrator ever refused Adu Bagong[6] clip request from one of the audience because the fight was felt too rough to aired.

Mandala TV receives greetings from the audience, then aired on running text. There are no specific schedules to airs greetings from the audience. Mandala TV applies greetings broadcast system which usually found on radio[3]. Mandala TV's flexibility and the easiness of the audience interacting with administrator makes greetings aired easily. The scope of audience which is in one area makes greetings effectively aired, it's shown by how many greetings sent to Mandala TV.

Airing local event documentation, requests and greetings got positive response from the audience. It's shown by the audience feedback via short message service to the administrator. Football games and celebration of Independence day of Indonesia documentation requested to air by audience many times.

The Audience feedback delivered easily and quickly also the flexibility makes Mandala TV become an interactive medium. Mandala TV, connecting people through television as a medium, even though today's technology that allow two-way communication widely used. Mandala TV becomes a medium for delivering value and connecting people.

Mandala TV has a proximity value of Cikajang people because they operating at Cikajang, operated by local people and airing local content. This proximity becomes a strength of Mandala TV as local television, because Indonesia's televisions (which is the majority are national television) are Jakartacentric[4]. National television in Indonesia concentrates at

Jakarta with the employees generally from Java island, it's makes the contents they produce have culture and sociological bias[1].

National television has bigger capital to make their broadcast viewed by the entire Indonesian. National television also has a chance producing content better than local television with limited capital, especially entertainment. It's made local television had a hard time to compete with national television.

Indonesian Law (Undang-Undang Nomor 32 Tahun 2002) about broadcasting, regulating television could only airs locally, if they want to airs outside the broadcast area they should cooperate with a local station. But, in the practice, there are so many television aired nationally.

5. Conclusion

Mandala TV as local television doing broadcast practice with flexible and interactive. Called Flexible, because there are no rules, schedule, and gatekeeper in media broadcasting. Then interactive, because Mandala TV receive contents request and greeting from audience to aired. Mandala TV's broadcast practice is different with other television in Indonesia, which are dominated by national television. Its contents shown local television become medium, that can unite society.

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